

Editorial

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Population and urbanisation growth and climate change are probably a number of important drivers, which place an unprecedented pressure on the environment, community and infrastructure. Among these drivers, climate change is an outstanding contributor to the threat to the detriment of natural resources related to water, soil and air.

Investigation of "climate change and its impact" was one of the four institutions in the Brown International Advanced Research Institutes (BIARI) at Brown University in June 2016. This institution convened early career scholars and practitioners from around the world to address the challenges of adaptation and mitigation strategies against the adverse impacts of climate change. This was achieved through intensive discussion panels and various presentations across academic, professional and geographic boundaries.

At the end of the programme, participants were fully aware of the expertise of each other, which can be used to underpin future research and practical collaborations. The participants of the institution were then invited to submit a paper to a special issue of the Revista Espinhaço. As a result, five papers were accepted to be published in the Journal. The submitted papers cover a variety of subjects which are either directly or indirectly related to the causes and effects of climate change. More specifically, Escoto et al. discussed how growth of household power consumption can contribute to the increase in greenhouse gas emissions in Mexico. Juanamaria Vazquez discussed the public debate about use of genetically modified organisms and domestic native corn in agriculture in Mexico. Adesoji and Adejumo identified the sustainable practices of land management in Nigeria and associated factors led to the achievement of best practices (e.g. awareness and education). Elhadi also analysed how developing appropriate gender policies in organisations can improve management of natural resources and agricultural sectors under climate change stresses in Sudan. In addition, Silva et al. explore the chemical, mineralogical and physical characteristics of a material accumulated on the river margin from mud flowing from the collapse of the iron ore tailings dam in Bento Rodrigues, Minas Gerais, Brazil.

The purpose of the publications in this issue is to raise the value of such a multi-disciplinary analysis for climate change impacts and provide a scientific platform for those seeking knowledge, inspiration and professional guidance in this area. Obviously, this issue can be a good start in the journal and hence further publications in the relevant special issues would be necessary in the future. I look forward to working with experts in this multi-disciplinary environment to help us achieve a brighter future in which the most efficient adaptation and mitigation strategies of climate change can be identified and implemented.

This special issue also brings a very interesting interview with Dr. Bette Otto Bliesner. Dr. Bliesner is a researcher at the National Center for Atmospheric Research (NCAR) and expert in climate modeling and historic climate change. In this interview, she brings significant reflections about her recent work as an IPCC contributor. This interview was conducted by Kourosh Behzadian (University of West London), Douglas Sathler (FIH/Cegeo/UFVJM) and Lorena Fleury (UFRGS). In addition, Lilian Yamamoto reviewed the book written by Diogo Andreola Serraglio entitled "Environmental refugees by the international law"

I welcome your contributions and comments.